

Comparison of DC-DC converters for solar power conversion system

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ABSTRACT

This paper covers the comparison between four different DC-DC converters for solar power conversion. The four converters are buck converter, buck-boost converter, boost converter, and noninverting buck-boost converter. An maximum power point tracking (MPPT) algorithm is designed to calculate battery voltage, current of photovoltaic (PV) array, the voltage of PV array, power of PV array, output power. It is observed that the non-inverting buck-boost converter is the finest converter for solar power conversion. The final circuit design has the results of 12.2 V battery voltage, 0.31 A current of PV array, 34 V voltage of PV array, 23 mW power of PV panel, and 21.8 mW of output power. The efficiency of this system is nearly 95%. All four circuits are simulated in MATLAB/Simulink R2020b.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The world has a keen interest in collecting knowledge about the earth, its neighboring planets, and moons of different planets, the sun, and also different galaxies. This all can be possibly done by space exploration. NASA has done some phenomenal work on nuclear power systems [1]. Space exploration is done by satellites that need electrical power to do their required work [2]. In recent years there have been several satellites launched in space for scientific research [3], mobile communication, remote sensing, mapping of an area, navigation of ships, vehicles, planes, and drones. In space, satellites need electrical power which can only be provided by solar energy. Tennakoon *et al.* [4], there is an explanation about maximizing solar energy uses. Satellites need to convert solar energy to electrical energy and need to store energy to do their required work. Mars Rover is one of the examples of this process [5]. Some evolutionary computing techniques were also used to reduce the cost of satellites or other spacecraft [6]. The electric power system is explained in reference [7]. In the energy conversion process from solar to electric, DC microgrid and DC-DC converters come into play. Some research was also done for DC-microgrids for space application [8]. D'Antonio *et al.* [9], some mathematical approach was used to decrease the overall mass of the power system used in space exploration. Baharudin *et al.* [10] a photovoltaic (PV) power system is presented which is of high efficiency and has a very compact design. Several types of DC-DC converters can be used in solar power conversion microgrids [11].

A microgrid is a local energy grid that is self-sufficient and has control over itself. It can connect and disconnect from the main grid and can operate on its own. Renewable resources like wind energy, solar

panels can be used to power microgrids. It has many advantages including better power quality and being more environment friendly [12]. A microgrid can be constructed to run indefinitely if we know how it's fueled and how efficiently we can manage its requirements. Energy management strategies are used for maximum optimization of microgrids [13]. The isolation technology of microgrids makes it more reliable [14]. DC-DC converters are the circuits that are used to convert one dc voltage into another dc voltage. This converter can be used in very low voltage as well as very high voltage applications. These converters can boost solar energy up to 30% in solar applications. This type of converter can provide different voltages to different components of a system to gain maximum output from that system or to increase the overall performance of the system. It reduces conduction losses with optimum peak current to increase efficiency to maximum [15].

The solar microgrid can be designed by using maximum power point tracking (MPPT) technology. In this technology, PV panels relate to the DC-DC converter, and it is further connected to load or some energy storage device, and the MPPT controller is connected in parallel to the PV panels and series with the DC-DC converter. This method brings highly reliable, maintenance-free, and highly flexible operation to the system [16]. The MPPT controller is based on the MPPT algorithm [17]. This algorithm is applied in photovoltaic systems. The degree of sunlight falling on the PV panel (solar irradiance) always changes throughout the day, the tracker finds the sweet spot on the PV panel where the current and voltage is maximum. There are different MPPT algorithms, but the perturb and observe algorithm (P&O) method is the simplest [18]. The circuits of DC-DC converters are designed in MATLAB/Simulink and the MPPT algorithm is implemented for obtaining power from each converter. The efficiency graph obtained from Simulink is compared. The P&O method is used since it is reliable, and its hardware implementation is also simple.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Variable identification

In this research, to proceed further and apply the MPPT algorithm. The following variables need to be identified: PV voltage (v_{PV}), PV current (i_{PV}), PV power (p_{PV}), output current (I_{out}), output voltage or battery voltage (V_{out}), and output power (P_{out}). The v_{PV} and i_{PV} can also be referred to as input voltage and input current respectively for DC-DC converters.

2.2. MPPT algorithm

The P&O method of the MPPT algorithm is used [19], [20] since there is no complex computation, and its hardware implementation is also simple. Some papers research the evaluation of the P&O method [21], [22]. There are other methods to optimize the system like the MPSO method based on the MPPT algorithm [23]. The MPPT function block where MPPT code is written is shown in Figure 1. The P&O method is explained in the flowchart given in Figure 2.

Figure 1 depicts the MPPT function block and pulse width modulation (PWM) generator block. The MPPT function is written for the MPPT block and v_{PV} and i_{PV} is given as input and duty is taken out as output. Further, the duty output is the input for the PWM generator and PWM is coming out as output is further transferred to the MOSFET of the converter [24], [25]. Figure 2 depicts the flowchart of the algorithm used in the MPPT function. The algorithm starts by reading v_{PV} and i_{PV} from solar panels and setting the maximum power to initial value (usually zero). Then we need old and new values of voltage and power to calculate the difference between them because this algorithm searches for derivatives of power with respect to voltage (i.e. dP/dV). Then it checks If $dP/dV = 0$ duty will not change and if the old value power is not equal to the new value of power and PV voltage greater than 30 V then the algorithm will work, and the final duty will be computed.

Figure 1. MPPT function and PWM generator

Figure 2. Flowchart of P&O Method of MPPT algorithm

2.3. Circuit design and simulation

The circuit is designed in MATLAB/Simulink. The PV modules integrated with DC-DC converters are classified into two groups: full power and partial power conversion and full power conversion [26]. The DC-DC converters can be cascaded with PV modules [27]. Some connections problems arise due to cascading DC-DC converters whose solution can be found in reference [28]. When DC-DC converters are added on the PV module level there is a large amount of power dropped off the whole PV system [29]. The circuit diagrams of buck, boost, and buck-boost is stated in [30]–[32]. Narasimha and Salkuti [33], a detailed analysis of the buck-boost converter is presented. The PV panel, DC-DC converter, and load are connected in series. The output coming out of the MPPT function is given to the PWM generator and the output coming out of it is given to the metal oxide semiconductor field effect transistor (MOSFET) of the converter in Figure 1. Different combinations of resistance, capacitor, and inductor are used to obtain maximum efficiency from each converter. Figure 3 depicts buck topology, Figure 4 depicts boost topology, Figure 5 depicts buck-boost topology, and Figure 6 depicts non-inverting buck-boost topology. The values of resistance, capacitor, and inductor are shown in Figures 3-6 of each circuit diagram. The values of capacitor and inductor for non-inverting buck-boost are $C_i = 4 \mu F$, $L = 122 \mu H$, $C_o = 7 \mu F$.

Figure 3 depicts the circuit of the buck converter. The irradiance curve and temperature are given as the input to the PV array block. The PV array block is cascaded with a buck converter and load. After simulation, V_{out} and I_{out} are obtained from using a scope. It is known that the product of voltage and current gives power. Then output current and output voltage are simulated through a multiplier and power is obtained similarly the power of a PV panel is obtained by multiplying i_{PV} and v_{PV} . The obtained value of $v_{PV} = 33.9$ V, $i_{PV} = 0.239$ A, $V_{out} = 9.6$ V, $I_{out} = 0.48$ A, $p_{PV} = 0.012$ W, $P_{out} = 0.0112$ W, $C_i = 100 \mu F$, $L = 783 \mu H$, $C_o = 36400 \mu F$.

Figure 4 depicts the circuit of the boost converter. The irradiance curve and temperature are given as the input to the PV array block. Then the PV array block is cascaded with a boost converter and load. After simulation, V_{out} and I_{out} are obtained from using a scope. It is known that the product of voltage and current gives power. Then output current and output voltage are simulated through a multiplier and power is obtained similarly the power of a PV panel is obtained by multiplying i_{PV} and v_{PV} . The obtained value of $v_{PV} = 4.37$ V, $i_{PV} = 0.258$ A, $V_{out} = 4.37$ V, $I_{out} = 0.0027$ A, $p_{PV} = 0.0031$ W, $P_{out} = 0.0027$ W, $C_i = 100 \mu F$, $L = 0.002 \mu H$, $C_o = 100 \mu F$.

Figure 5 depicts the buck-boost converter circuit. The irradiance curve and temperature are given as the input to the PV array block. Then the PV array block is cascaded with a buck-boost converter and load. After simulation, V_{out} and I_{out} are obtained from using a scope. It is known that the product of voltage and current gives power. Then output current and output voltage are simulated through a multiplier and power is obtained similarly the power of a PV panel is obtained by multiplying i_{PV} and v_{PV} . The obtained value of

$v_{PV} = 5.6 \text{ V}$, $i_{PV} = 0.25 \text{ A}$, $V_{out} = 4.7 \text{ V}$, $I_{out} = 0.23 \text{ A}$, $p_{PV} = 0.00406 \text{ W}$, $P_{out} = 0.0032 \text{ W}$, $C_i = 100 \mu\text{F}$, $L = 783 \mu\text{H}$, $C_o = 100 \mu\text{F}$.

Figure 6 depicts the circuit of a noninverting buck-boost converter. The irradiance curve and temperature are given as the input to the PV array block. Then the PV array block is cascaded with a noninverting buck-boost converter and load. After simulation, V_{out} and I_{out} are obtained from using a scope. It is known that the product of voltage and current gives power. Then output current and output voltage are simulated through a multiplier and power is obtained similarly the power of a PV panel is obtained by multiplying v_{PV} and i_{PV} . The obtained value of $v_{PV} = 34 \text{ V}$, $i_{PV} = 0.31 \text{ A}$, $V_{out} = 12.2 \text{ V}$, $I_{out} = 0.61 \text{ A}$, $p_{PV} = 0.02302 \text{ W}$, $P_{out} = 0.02185 \text{ W}$, $C_i = 4 \mu\text{F}$, $L = 122 \mu\text{H}$, $C_o = 7 \mu\text{F}$.

Figure 3. Buck topology

Figure 4. Boost topology

Figure 5. Buck-boost topology

Figure 6. Noninverting buck-boost topology

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The circuits are simulated for 0.6 seconds in MATLAB/Simulink. The values of each variable are calculated from the graphs of each variable. The root mean square (RMS) value is calculated from each graph. The graph of efficiency is also obtained by using this formula of efficiency in MATLAB/Simulink i.e. ($\text{eff} = (\text{Pout}/\text{Pin}) * 100$). The results obtained from the simulation are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Values of variables

Variable	Buck	Boost	Buck-Boost	NIBB
V_{out} [V]	9.6	4.37	4.7	12.2
p_{PV} [W]	0.012	0.0031	0.0032	0.023
v_{PV} [V]	33.9	4.37	5.6	34
P_{out} [W]	0.0112	0.0027	0.0032	0.02185
i_{PV} [A]	0.239	0.258	0.25	0.31
I_{out} [A]	0.48	0.0027	0.23	0.61

Table 1 shows the value of parameters or variables. These values are calculated from a graph of each variable. First, the scope block is used in Simulink to obtain the graph then we used the signal statistic tool to get the root mean square value of the given graph. The graph of each variable is obtained by simulating the circuits in MATLAB/Simulink. Using the values of variables, efficiency is calculated. After the simulation the values of input current, input voltage are taken and given to multiplier to calculate input power, and similarly, the output power is calculated then from using a scope, graphs of both the power are obtained from which we have computed the RMS value of both input and output power. By taking the ratio of output power and input power, efficiency is calculated.

3.1. Efficiency

The graph of Pin/Pout ratio vs time graph of four different converters is obtained by using the Maximum point tracking algorithm in MATLAB/Simulink. The formula used for calculating efficiency is $P_{out}/p_{PV} * 100\%$. In Figure 7, for the boost converter, the efficiency is nearly 87%. In Figure 8, it can be seen that the buck converter efficiency is nearly 93%. In Figure 9 we can see that the buck-boost converter efficiency is nearly 78%. From Figure 10, it can be observed that the efficiency of noninverting buck-boost converters is nearly 95%.

Figure 7 depicts the efficiency vs time curve of the boost converter. The x-axis is efficiency (ratio of output and input power) and the y-axis is for the time in seconds. It can be seen from the graph that it initially starts from zero and goes upto 0.5 in a short interval of time then it remains nearly constant upto 0.45 seconds and then goes upto 0.9 at 0.6 seconds. When the RMS value of the graph is calculated using Simulink it comes out to be 0.56. When the efficiency of the boost converter is calculated from the formula $(\text{Pout}/\text{Pin} * 100)$, it comes out to be nearly 87%.

Figure 8 depicts the efficiency vs time curve of boost topology. The x-axis is of efficiency (ratio of output and input power) and the y-axis is for the time in seconds. It can be seen from the graph that it initially starts from zero and goes upto 0.5 in the short interval of time then it remains nearly constant upto 0.4 seconds then it falls to 0.1 in a very short period of time and then goes upto 0.8 at 0.6 seconds. When the RMS value of the graph is calculated using Simulink it comes out to be 0.0032. When the efficiency of the buck-boost converter is calculated from the formula $(\text{Pout}/\text{Pin} * 100)$, it comes out to be nearly 78%.

Figure 9 depicts the efficiency vs time curve of buck topology. The x-axis is efficiency (ratio of output and input power) and the y-axis is for the time in seconds. This graph fluctuates very fast. It starts from zero then it reaches upto 0.7 in 0.35 seconds then comes down to 0 at 0.3 seconds then it reaches 0.9 at 0.35 seconds then again it comes down to zero in a very short period and then it fluctuated more between 0 and 0.9 and finally get saturated near 0.9 at 0.6 seconds. When the RMS value of the graph is calculated using Simulink it comes out to be 3.4. When the efficiency of the buck topology is calculated from the formula $(\text{Pout}/\text{Pin} * 100)$, it comes out to be nearly 93%.

Figure 10 depicts the efficiency vs time curve of a non-inverting buck-boost converter. The x-axis is efficiency (ratio of output and input power) and the y-axis is for the time in seconds. The signal in this graph fluctuates more than the buck topology. It starts from 0 then goes upto 0.5 in 0.1 seconds and reach zero in a very short period of time then goes upto 0.6 remains constant for a short period of time then comes to 0.1 in 0.25 seconds and goes above 1.6 in a very short period of time then after oscillating comes down to 0.7 in 0.35 seconds then it fluctuates between zero and 1.6 for more 0.1 seconds and get saturated at 0.95. When the RMS value of the graph is calculated using Simulink it comes out to be 4.3. When the efficiency of the non-inverting buck-boost topology is calculated from the formula $(\text{Pout}/\text{Pin} * 100)$, it comes out to be nearly 95%.

After simulating each circuit in MATLAB/Simulink, the RMS value of the graph (efficiency vs time) is observed. The RMS value can be acquired by using the signal statistic tool present in the Simulink. The RMS values obtained are 3.4 for the buck converter, 0.56 for the boost converter, 0.0032 for the buck-boost converter, and 4.3 for the non-inverting buck-boost converter. From these results, we can also say that the non-inverting buck-boost converter has the highest RMS value so it is most efficient.

Figure 7. Boost topology efficiency

Figure 8. Buck-boost topology efficiency

Figure 9. Buck topology efficiency

Figure 10. Non-inverting buck-boost topology efficiency

4. CONCLUSION

This paper presents the comparison of the efficiency of four converters i.e. boost, buck-boost, buck, and non-inverting buck-boost converters. An MPPT algorithm is designed which uses the P&O method to maximize the output power and to obtain maximum efficiency. All the circuits are designed in MATLAB/Simulink and each circuit is simulated to obtain a graph of the efficiency of each converter. The values of variables are calculated using simulation results. The efficiency of each converter is calculated and

compared. The result is that the non-inverting buck-boost converter shows a maximum efficiency of nearly 95%. After all the analysis, the system parameters were 12.2 V load voltage or battery voltage, 0.31 A current of PV array, 34 V voltage of PV array, 23 mW power of PV array, and 21.8 mW of output power.

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